

Negotiating Uncertainty: Brazil's Strategic Autonomy in a Contested Global Landscape

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Abstract

Amid intensifying great power rivalry and the progressive erosion of the liberal rules-based order, this paper introduces the concept of "adaptive autonomy" to analyze Brazil's contemporary foreign policy posture. Defined as a composite strategic behavior practiced simultaneously across geoeconomic, crisis management, and institutional dimensions, adaptive autonomy integrates Kuik's hedging framework with the Active Non-Alignment doctrine theorized by Fortín, Heine, and Ominami, grounded in the historical periodization developed by Lessa and Doratioto (2025). The paper argues that behavioral flexibility in bilateral relationships, strategic distancing under normative pressure, and normative entrepreneurship in multilateral governance are mutually constitutive dimensions of a single coherent posture, whose analytical logic is assessed against its structural limits and comparative scope.

Keywords: Brazilian Foreign Policy; Strategic Autonomy; Hedging; Active Non-Alignment; Middle Powers; US-China Rivalry

Amid the progressive erosion of the liberal rules-based order and the intensification of US-China systemic rivalry, this paper introduces the concept of *adaptive autonomy* to analyze Brazil's contemporary foreign policy posture. The central argument holds that Brazil practices a composite, historically grounded strategic behavior simultaneously across three mutually constitutive dimensions: the geoeconomic, the crisis management, and the institutional. This posture integrates,

through an analytical move not previously attempted in the literature, Cheng-Chwee Kuik's hedging framework with the Active Non-Alignment (ANA) doctrine theorized by Fortín, Heine, and Ominami, anchored in the long-run historical periodization reconstructed by Lessa and Doratioto (2025).

The paper's core contribution is to demonstrate that behavioral flexibility in bilateral relationships, strategic distancing under normative pressure, and normative entrepreneurship in multilateral governance are not alternative expressions of autonomous agency but mutually constitutive dimensions of a single coherent posture whose logic becomes visible only when the three dimensions are examined together.

The paper's point of departure is the emergence of what Belmonte and Cerny (2021) characterize as a heterarchical world order: diffuse, contested, and multi-nodal, without consolidating in any single hegemonic architecture capable of imposing binding rules on its principal members. For Global South middle powers, this is not a distant systemic development but the defining structural condition within which foreign policy choices are formulated and autonomous agency negotiated daily. Brazil occupies a singular position within this condition: its material weight, diplomatic tradition, and location at the intersection of US-China rivalry make it simultaneously a meaningful interlocutor for competing great powers and a meaningful participant in alternative governance frameworks. The dilemma it confronts is the most demanding available: how to preserve independent agency, maintain access to the resources development requires, and advance national interests in a systemic environment where the costs of both alignment and non-alignment are rising simultaneously.

The paper reconceptualizes strategic autonomy as a dynamic, adaptive process of risk management rather than a fixed condition or juridical posture to be defended. Kuik's hedging framework provides the primary theoretical instrument, defining hedging as the simultaneous pursuit of returns-maximizing options, including binding engagement and limited bandwagoning, alongside risk-contingency options such as indirect balancing and dominance denial, while preserving a fallback position throughout (Kuik 2008, 2016, 2021).

The concept of *riskification* (Kuik 2023) adds an indispensable perceptual dimension: states perceive external threats not in binary terms but as a spectrum of risks with constantly shifting forms and intensities, each requiring distinct combinations of accommodation and resistance across multiple domains simultaneously. Active Non-Alignment, as elaborated by Fortín, Heine, and Ominami (2020, 2023), complements and extends this framework by transforming equidistance from a reactive posture defined by what states refuse to do into a proactive strategy defined by what they actively pursue: the deliberate mobilization of positional independence as leverage for normative entrepreneurship, coalition-

building, and collective amplification of national agency in multilateral arenas. Adaptive autonomy articulates these two frameworks into a synthesis that is constitutively multi-domain, non-declaratory, and historically grounded in a manner that no previous formulation in the hedging or ANA literatures has attempted.

Before examining contemporary dimensions, the paper reconstructs the historical substrate that makes the concept analytically meaningful. Drawing on Lessa and Doratioto (2025), it traces successive modalities of autonomous agency from the imperial period through the present, demonstrating that the preservation of independent maneuver capacity has functioned as a foundational national interest consistently prioritized across radically distinct domestic regimes and systemic configurations. The Rio Branco model of strategic pragmatism, Vargas's compensatory autonomy exploiting great power competition for material extraction, the Independent Foreign Policy of the Quadros and Goulart administrations anticipating ANA's proactive logic, Geisel's "Responsible Pragmatism" (Pragmatismo Responsável) as the first systematic management of the tension between interdependence and strategic independence, and the post-Cold War experiments in autonomy through engagement under Cardoso and South-South expansion under the PT administrations collectively constitute the long-run substrate from which adaptive autonomy emerges as contemporary reconfiguration rather than rupture.

The geoeconomic dimension reveals how Brazil navigates the entrapment versus abandonment dilemma generated by US-China rivalry through deliberate bilateral redundancy. The structural asymmetry is quantified through data from the Banco Central do Brasil (2025), UN COMTRADE (2024), ECLAC (2025), and CEBC (2025): China receives Brazilian exports of approximately USD 100 billion annually and constitutes its largest trading partner, while the United States remains the largest single-country investor with cumulative FDI stock of approximately USD 208 billion. Brazil is more commercially dependent on China and more financially integrated with the United States; neither power can credibly offer what the other provides, making bilateral redundancy a structural interest rather than a diplomatic preference (Atkinson and Silva 2025; Cook et al. 2025). The 5G spectrum auction of 2021 to 2022 illustrates adaptive autonomy under technological securitization: rather than acceding to Washington's demand for Huawei's full exclusion or resisting it entirely, Brazil structured the auction to exclude Huawei from the most sensitive core network components while preserving its participation in less strategically exposed segments, satisfying neither great power fully but preserving access to both relationships, the textbook expression of the *riskification* logic Kuik (2023) describes.

Comparative analysis with India, constrained by direct territorial contestation with China into a harder hedging variant incorporating Quad membership (Zajączkowski

and Pulami 2025), and with Turkey, whose multi-directional engagement ultimately produced costs in all directions simultaneously (Kutlay and Öniş 2021), confirms that Brazil's geoeconomic position is structurally more favorable: no territorial disputes with any great power, geographic distance from the primary theaters of US-China competition, and a diversified external economic structure that provides wider operational space for hedging than either comparator commands.

The crisis dimension, examined through two analytically paired cases, demonstrates that strategic distancing functions as an active diplomatic resource rather than an ethical vacuum. Russia's invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 confronted Brazil with the most demanding normative test the post-Cold War era had produced: a comprehensive alignment architecture backed by unprecedented Western sanctions and framed in categorical terms admitting few qualified responses. Brazil's posture combined formal condemnation, including the March 2022 UN General Assembly vote demanding Russia's withdrawal, making Brazil the only BRICS member to vote affirmatively, with systematic refusal to endorse sanctions, active promotion of negotiated solutions, and the cultivation of a mediatory identity grounded in non-alignment credentials.

Brazil's structural reliance on Russian fertilizer exports, accounting for 71 percent of Brazilian imports from Russia in 2022 and indispensable to the agricultural complex generating the country's export revenues and food security, constituted a genuine material constraint, not a pretext for diplomatic convenience, that Western interlocutors systematically underweighted (Belém Lopes and Vazquez 2024). The "sovereignty paradox" this generated, the coexistence of normative defense of Ukrainian territorial integrity with refusal to impose material costs on Russia for violating it, was in fact the operational expression of a coherent adaptive autonomy calculus, not a contradiction. The US military intervention in Venezuela on January 3, 2026, Operation Absolute Resolve resulting in the capture and extradition of President Nicolás Maduro, added a geographically proximate and normatively distinct test. President Lula's unequivocal condemnation and Brazil's participation in a joint regional rejection statement alongside Spain, Chile, Colombia, Mexico, and Uruguay applied structurally the same hedging posture as the Ukraine case, but under conditions generating broader cross-partisan domestic solidarity around non-intervention norms, suggesting that adaptive autonomy's domestic viability is more robust when the crisis directly implicates regional sovereignty than when it involves geographically remote confrontations where material interests and ideological alignments diverge.

The institutional dimension reveals how Brazil converts positional independence into governance influence through BRICS, G20 leadership, and unilateral coalitions. Brazilian diplomacy has consistently treated BRICS not as ideological alignment with a post-Western order but as institutional hedging in Kuik's sense: diversifying strategic partnerships, constructing alternative fallback positions, and

amplifying leverage through coordinated collective action, consistently positioning the grouping as a platform for reforming rather than dismantling international institutions (Stuenkel 2024).

Brazil's G20 presidency in 2024, organized around global wealth taxation, multilateral development bank reform, and a Global Alliance Against Hunger and Poverty, exemplified the ANA logic identified by Fortín, Heine, and Ominami (2023): the transformation of positional independence into normative leverage, using the credibility of equidistance to advance reformist agendas neither great power bloc can easily veto or capture. Results were mixed, as they typically are when middle powers attempt to move large multilateral institutions; a non-binding agreement on wealth taxation represented a normative milestone, but binding commitments remained elusive, partly because the structural gap between institutional ambition and effective material capabilities identified by Schenoni et al. (2022) limits follow-through capacity.

The structural limits of adaptive autonomy deserve equal analytical weight. The viability of hedging depends on conditions subject to erosion as US-China rivalry intensifies: progressive securitization of economic interdependence narrows space for bilateral redundancy; polarization of multilateral institutions reduces traction for normative entrepreneurship; domestic political fragmentation erodes the elite consensus on which sustained autonomous postures depend (Kuik and Jamil 2024). The risk of foreign policy overstretch, multiplying institutional commitments without proportional resource investment and producing diffuse engagement that amplifies visibility without generating commensurate influence, remains the most trenchant structural warning (Schenoni et al. 2022).

Adaptive autonomy is not a guarantee of influence, not a costless strategy, and not a permanent equilibrium. It is an indispensable survival mechanism for middle powers whose structural position places them at the intersection of competing great power demands without the material capabilities to impose their own preferences on the systemic environment. That Brazil has practiced something recognizable as adaptive autonomy for the better part of two centuries suggests the underlying strategic logic is durable in ways that transcend any particular administration's ideological commitments, constituting a conceptual vocabulary for understanding how states negotiate uncertainty, manage dependency, and preserve agency in a world order whose rules remain, as they have long been, an object of geopolitical contestation rather than a settled inheritance.

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